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Preface

This volume contains the papers presented at Doctoral Symposium of the Society 5.0 Conference 2024, hosted by the University of Technology in Mauritius and supported by the University of Pretoria, South Africa. This multi- and interdisciplinary conference is continuing to grow into a premier international conference series and is jointly organized by the University of Pretoria (South Africa), the FHNW University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland, the University of Camerino (Italy), the Universidad EAFIT (Colombia), the Business School of the Shenzhen Technology University (China), the Universiti Malaysia Kelantan (Malaysia), and Putra Business School (Malaysia).

We are living in an era with technologies available for software, hardware and data interconnectedness that are and will dictate the agenda for the future creating both challenges and opportunities for a Society 5.0. No doubt, words echoed in the New Delhi G20 Summit like the need for Creating a more Inclusive World, Driving Gender Inclusive Climate Action, Bridging the Gender Digital Divide, and Harnessing Artificial Intelligence responsibly for the Good and for all have set the agenda rolling. We are at a juncture in history where the decisions we make now will determine the future of our people and our planet. Together we have an opportunity to build a better future. We have to pursue development models that implement sustainable, inclusive and just transitions globally while leaving no one behind. Improving access to digital services and digital public infrastructure and leveraging digital transformation opportunities to boost sustainable and inclusive growth may have to dictate the agenda for innovation so that we can promote sustainable, quality, healthy, safe and gainful employment. Innovations for sustainable and inclusive Social Good are essential for addressing the complex challenges facing our world and building a more equitable and environmentally responsible future. This conference provides the opportunity to make a meaningful contribution to Society 5.0 in the making.

For the 2024 Society 5.0 conference we encouraged contributions from experienced and young researchers and practitioners from industry. At the Doctoral Symposium four PhD candidates presented the current status of their work. For each PhD candidate there was a mentor who provided feedback to the first submission and the the presentation. The updated submissions are collected in this volume of the conference proceedings.

Thank you to all the mentors and participants of the Doctoral Symposium.

September 28, 2024

Knut Hinkelmann
Hanlie Smuts

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Continuous Assessment Learning Activity Implications on Quality of Basic Education in Chikomba District, Zimbabwe

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Abstract. Zimbabwe adopted a new perspective of continuous assessment in 2015. However, due to myriads of constraints CALA was shelved for certification as from intended year, 2015 until 2021 to date. It was implemented as part of certification for completion of Elementary, Ordinary and Advanced level courses. Under this CALA framework, the teacher has to set five research based activities drawn from syllabus. Teacher shall mark the tasks, convert to percentage and record average of the marks. The mark is then send to Zimbabwe School Examination Council for certification and it constitute 30% while the reminder 70% is for summative mark. Thus, this study seeks to explore key tenets of quality basic education, examine the link between CALA and quality basic education, analyse the challenges faced by learners and teachers in the implementation of CALA in secondary schools and to establish strategies and a framework or model for solving CALA limitations to quality basic education. Research methodology to be adopted is mixed. This implies that, both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods are to be used jointly or sequentially in unpacking all five stated research objectives. Data collection tools that shall be used are interviews, focus group discussions and questionnaires. Data analysis to be done using Statistical Package for Social Sciences, descriptive statistics inform of mean, mode, histograms, pie charts, pairwise ranking matrix and thematic analysis. This study is important as it informs policy makers in Zimbabwe about the challenges hindering effective implementation of CALA and recommendations that can be adopted.

Key words: Continuous Assessment Learning Activity, Implications, Quality, Basic Education

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1 Introduction and Background of the Study

Continuous Assessment Learning Activity, (CALA) as an educational public policy for quality basic education has been a domain of major concern across the globe. Accordingly, countless strenuous efforts have been effected to embrace quality of basic education. This actually necessitated the inclusion of Sustainable Development Goal 4 for quality education by United Nations (UN) in September 2015 [21]. In line with this international perspective, most countries in various continents have implemented CALA in their basic education. In Europe, Greece is one of the leading countries that adopted measures to improve quality basic education. At the heart of these steps was the incorporation of formative assessments [16]. As a result, one of the key outcomes of their study buttresses the need for learner centred approaches on research based continuous assessments assigned.

In addition to that, attempts were also appropriated in Asia by Pakistan in implementation of CALA. Thus, a study was conducted to examine the impacts of Continuous Assessment Methods on learners' ability at primary level at Lahore [12]. Key findings revealed that continuous assessment improves academic performance of learners which has a positive bearing on quality basic education [12]. This concurs with results that were also obtained in Nepal, Asia. Accordingly, a study was carried out for Grade Four students in Sunsari District [9]. The aim was based on comparing the Mathematics achievement of Continuous Assessment System (CAS) student and non CAS student. Results indicated better achievement in Mathematics for students with CAS and lower marks for non-CAS marks [9]. This demonstrates the significance of continuous assessment in improving understanding of learners and quality basic education.

In Africa, there were many Sub-Saharan countries that adopted Continuous Assessment Learning Activities in their elementary and secondary levels [4]. This concurs with the views that, African countries have embraced Continuous Assessment Learning Activities copying it from More Economically Developed Countries (MEDCs) and newly developed [22]. These countries include but not limited to Uganda, Ethiopia, Ghana, South Africa and Nigeria [1-4,17]. For instance, in Ethiopia a study highlighted that, implementation of CALA on Sports Science learners in basic education improves skills, performance, learner's engagement and motivation [3]. This will in a long run facilitate pupils to identify their inherent strengths and limitations hence quality basic education [3]. This is also in tantamount with the results obtained in Uganda's Kabale Municipality primary schools on the effects of CALA on pupils' academic performance [2]. The research concluded that CALA improves academic performance of learners due to increased assignments and learner's engagement. The results are also in line with findings from Asia specifically in Pakistan and Nepal [9,12].

On contrary, CALA was perceived to jeopardize quality basic education in some African countries notably in Ethiopia and Nigeria. A study carried out in Chagni City Administration, Ethiopia on the impacts of CALA to elementary education depicted negative results [17]. They were chiefly caused by the failure of educators to strictly follow what CALA policies demand in reality in schools [17]. This is also in line with

findings from Nigeria in Obowo local government area of Imo State. CALA was not well implemented due to shortage of trained educators, being expensive to manage, requiring a lot of time and energy, too much paper work and that its demands were difficult and complex to implement [1]. As a result, this research is of paramount significance to add knowledge to existing literature. This is highly imperative taking into cognisance that, Zimbabwe for the first time in history, incorporated continuous assessments and summative assessments for certification of grade 7, form 4 and 6 examination classes in 2021, 2022 and 2023 [11]. In addition to that, the study is crucial at least as the first one in Chikomba District to ascertain the implications of this new educational public policy. This should be done taking into account the fundamental differences in political, economic, socio-cultural and technological that exist in Europe, Asia and other fellow African countries with that of Zimbabwe, hence the research is worth undertaking.

In Zimbabwe, CALA public educational policy was introduced as one of the notable key change of the new curriculum. This was implemented partly in line with the recommendations of the commission of inquiry that was established by the government [15]. It entirely advocates for outcome-based curriculum. It also criticised old curriculum of being too much theoretical by relying on summative assessments only which produce learners who are unable to solve real life problems [15]. In addition to the core cause, locally, Zimbabwe introduced new curriculum in line with National Development Strategy (NDS1) policy document [11]. This blueprint calls for Zimbabwe to be a middle-class economy by 2030 which should be attained through education for industrial development [11]. Thus, as from 2014, the Ministry of Primary and Secondary (MoPSE) initiated on a detailed national curriculum overhaul to enhance basic quality education in Zimbabwe [10]. Several innovations were introduced in the new curriculum with broad implications for stakeholders at all levels [11].

Despite the new curriculum framework being launched in 2015, CALA was finally implemented by Zimbabwe School Examination Council, (ZIMSEC) for certification of Grade 7, Forms 4 and 6 examination classes in 2021. The prime objective of CALA was for learners to perform, demonstrate their knowledge, understanding and proficiency in their learning areas before summative assessment [10]. Under this model, continuous assessment coursework constitutes 30% and summative assessment 70% for each learning area [10]. The main thrust was to achieve quality education by producing students who are capable of applying skills acquired to solve practical problems there by sustaining a decent living [10]. This is also in line with the sentiments that, the entire importance of CALA is the merging of theory and practical experience [22]. Zhao further pinpoints that the goodness of continuous assessment in a learning area will never be compromised if properly articulated. Therefore, this study is critical to sniff out the implications of this newly introduced curriculum policy as a first of its kind since attainment of independence in 1980 and given contradicting positive and hast experience in some fellow African nations.

2 Statement of the Problem

Zimbabwe is battling to improve quality basic education through newly introduced CALA public educational policy as it is populated with numerous myriads of challenges [13]. These constraints include limited time for learners to complete tasks, failure by teachers to complete the syllabuses, corruption by teachers and students and learners being overburdened with a lot of tasks [13]. It further postulates other constraints associated with CALA implementation as to be hinged on lack of training on the part teachers, lack of supervision on standardisation of CALAs and shortage of resources. This is in tantamount with the utterances that, the rationale for CALA implementation was highly compromised as the updated curriculum requirements were associated with a lot of implementation requirements that many could not afford [18].

It further, specifies the necessities that were out of reach to many learners as shortage of ICT tools and gadgets, lack of phones with internet access, high cost of data charges especially for the poor and marginalised minority communities and digital infrastructure in schools. Thus, in this scenario, fundamental stakeholders such as parents, teachers and learners felt that CALA was leaving out the existing vulnerable marginalised and disabled hence, then it must be removed [18]. This is also tantamount to the views that, absence of prerequisites for CALA implementation has caused unjustified pressure on key educational stakeholders [19]. Above all, at one point in time, the Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education was dragged to court by stakeholders who were totally against the implementation of this updated curriculum and argued for its temporary abandonment [14]. Based on the divergent perspectives above, it can be concluded that more needs to be done in various capacities to achieve the intended yields of CALA in basic education. It is against this background that, the researcher decides to carry out a detailed study on the implications of CALA with the view to achieve quality basic education in Zimbabwe.

3 Research Objectives

The overall objective of the study is to analyse CALA implications on quality of basic education in Chikomba District, Zimbabwe. Accordingly, specific main objectives of the study are to:

- i. Explore key tenets of quality basic education in line with international best practices.
- ii. Examine the link between CALA and quality basic education.
- iii. Analyse the challenges faced by learners in the implementation of CALA in secondary schools.
- iv. Assess the problems faced by teachers in the implementation of CALA in secondary schools.
- v. Establish strategies and a framework or model for solving CALA limitations to quality basic education in Zimbabwe.

4 Research Questions

Accordingly, the objectives would rationally respond to the research questions as to:

- i. What are the key tenets of quality basic education in line with international best practices?
- ii. What is the link between CALA and quality basic education?
- iii. What are the challenges faced by learners in the implementation of CALA in secondary schools?
- iv. What are the problems faced by teachers in the implementation of CALA in secondary schools?
- v. What are strategies and a framework or model for solving CALA limitations to quality basic education in Zimbabwe?

5 Methodological Approach Used

5.1 Research Design

Research design is defined as a model of ways and methods selected by the researcher to merge several elements of study in a sensibly coherent way so that the research challenge is adequately and effectively tackled [8]. Furthermore, it involves all other component parts of research, such variables, hypotheses, experiments, methodology and statistical analysis [6]. A research design is of paramount significance as it facilitates the uncovering of processes and logistical set ups to start a study [8]. In this study, cross-sectional research design was utilised for the phenomena studied. It was used as cross-sectional studies are cheaper, less time consuming than many other types of study, they allow to easily collect data that can be used as a basis for further research [20]. It further seeks to record the information that is readily available in a population at a single time without manipulation of variables [20]. Thus, cross section research design also adds knowledge to already existing ones.

5.2 Research Approach

Mixed research method is to be adopted in this study. Mixed-methods research (MMR) is a research methodology that incorporates multiple methods to address research questions in an appropriate and principled manner [5]. This implies that both qualitative and quantitative data collection methods were used jointly or sequentially in unpacking research objectives as indicated in section 1.3. Key strengths of mixed approach include complementary through triangulation of two approaches namely qualitative and quantitative. This means that, the net disadvantages of one method is mitigated by another and vice versa hence enhancing validity and reliability [7]. Though the merits of mixed methodology are quite convincing, it has some limitations. These include lack of time, energy and resources [23]. The researcher shall overcome some of the limitations by being granted Manpower Development Leave (MDL) to create more time to undertake the research as well as saving from his

income streams to fund the research related costs. Consequently, it can be deduced that the demerits are outweighed by the advantages hence the adoption of the mixed method research approach.

5.3 Data Collection Tools

In this study, during pilot research and the entire course of the study, the researcher shall use questionnaires, focus groups and key informant interviews. These shall be utilised to extract data from respondents, namely learners, teachers, parents and school heads. Additionally, Chikomba District Supervisory Inspector (DSI), Chikomba District Secondary Inspectors, Provincial Educational officers and ZIMSEC provincial officers. Above all, MoPSE Head office officials, Teacher’s union leaders in Chikomba District, renowned educationists and educational based charity organisations for children in Chikomba district.

5.4 Data Analysis Framework

The summary of the research objectives, the respective variables under study and the several tools for data analysis which shall be used in this study is as shown in Table 1.1 below.

Table 3.4 Data analysis Framework.

Research objective	Variables	Analytical tools
1. To explore key tenets of quality basic education.	Teacher’s qualifications and experience, learning areas taught, resources, amount of research work, learner’s own new models, use of ICT tools.	Thematic analysis, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). (mean, mode, histograms, pie charts).
2. To analyse the link between CALA and quality basic education.	New models or initiatives, amount of research-based activities, pass rate, time, ICT tools used, resources, reported high workloads.	Thematic analysis SPSS,(mean, mode, histograms, pie charts).
3. To examine challenges faced by secondary schools learners during implementation of CALA.	Time, tasks, resources, reported failure to supervise learner’s tasks, cases of corruption, Covid-19, internet and ICT tools, infrastructure and cases of CALA missing marks, geographical location.	Thematic analysis Pairwise ranking matrix

<p>4. To determine challenges faced by secondary school teachers in the implementation of CALA in Zimbabwe.</p>	<p>Resources, time, qualifications, experience, workloads, salaries, infrastructure, teacher pupil ratio, CALA missing marks, ICT tools and number of learners failing to complete CALA tasks.</p>	<p>Thematic analysis Pairwise ranking matrix</p>
<p>5. To establish strategies for effective CALA implementation in secondary schools of Zimbabwe.</p>	<p>Training, resources, salaries, employment of staff, digital infrastructure, records keeping, monitoring and evaluation, educational policies and legislation.</p>	<p>Thematic analysis SPSS (mean, mode, histograms, pie charts)</p>

6 Description of the Artefact

6.1 CALA Model in Zimbabwe

A framework was established called Assessment Model for assessing performance of learners in a learning area [10]. The model integrates both CALA with weight 100% and Summative Assessments with same weight of 100%. Additionally, it shows that, though CALA and summative marks constitute 100% each, the weight may be reduced to accommodate each other for certification. Thus, as from 2021 to 2023, CALA constituted 30% and summative examinations 70% for grade 7, forms 4 and 6 examination classes [11]. Furthermore, the framework also involves profiling of learners through proper record keeping. These records can be also used when a learner wishes to transfer. Additionally, emphasis is on learner exit profile upon completion, final mark for certification and learner profile certification. Fig 6.1 provides a summary of Assessment model in Zimbabwe.

Fig. 6.1: CALA Assessment Model in Zimbabwe. Source: (MOPSE, 2015)

7 Summary of Work done to date

The researcher physically attended three international conferences where he made oral presentations. These were: 1. Society 5.0 organised by University of Technology, Mauritius and University of Pretoria, South Africa. 2. International Conference on Future Education 2024 hosted by International Institute of Knowledge Management. 3. International Conference co-hosted by Manjara Charitable Trust and Mauritius Institute of Education. Accordingly, the researcher submitted 2 full research papers and 1 Doctoral Symposium which are under editorial team for publication. Moreover, the researcher has two accepted abstracts to be presented at international fora. The first one was accepted by University of Seychelles and the Orebro University. The researcher is working on the compilation of full research paper with his supervisor. The second one was accepted by University of Johannesburg and Mauritius Institute of Education and the researcher shall work on producing the full research paper. Currently he is on working on final drafts for chapter 2 and 3 which are Literature review and Research methodology respectively.

8 Expected Contribution of the Work

The work is expected to contribute in the following ways:

- a) Enlightening educational stakeholders especially learners, teachers, parents, educational unions, government and possible employers about some of the key tenets of quality education and how CALA best addresses those tenets.
- b) Informing the policy makers primarily in Zimbabwe such as those from MoPSE and ZIMSEC on the challenges being faced by teachers and learners in implementing CALA for quality basic education.
- c) Proposing strategies as recommendations to policy makers primarily in Zimbabwe such as those from MoPSE and ZIMSEC for realisation of quality basic education through CALA educational policies and supportive pieces of legislation.
- d) Alignment of education's system to meet national broad objectives of Zimbabwe as enshrined in National Development Strategy (NDS1 and NDS2) which were set for 2021 to 2025 and 2026 to 2030 timelines respectively.
- e) Establishing an educational system that is in line with envisioning Industry 5.0 which advocates for an well-equipped and adaptable workforce and Zimbabwe's Vision 2030 for it to be an middle upper class economy.
- f) It adds to the attainment of United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4) which advocates for quality education.
- g) Drawing of lessons from Zimbabwe by other countries regionally and globally with the view to improve their respective basic educational policies and legislations in their respective countries.

9 A Plan to ensure Research Transparency of my Work

The researcher shall secure clearance certificate to conduct research from University of Technology, Mauritius and Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education in Zimbabwe. Additionally, participants are given opportunity to decide freely whether to take part or not without being coerced. The researcher shall clearly explain the purpose of the research to enhance informed consent from the participants. Furthermore, special considerations to anonymity and confidentiality of the participants to be at the heart of the study. Moreover, the researcher to acknowledge all literature used properly and emphasise to be also on right to withdraw from the study and timely publication of the results.

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Implementation and Impact of Green Human Resource Management Practices for Employee Pro-Environmental Behavior in Tourist Hotels in Tanzania

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1 Background Information of the Study

Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) is defined as “policies and practices of human resource management used in the organisation to influence pro-environmental behaviour among employees to ensure environmental management and organisational competitiveness” [4, 6]. The concerns for environmental management pressured organisations to integrate human resource management functions with environmental issues [17, 20-21]. This is because climate change, global warming and environmental pollution attract global attention to society, governments and organisations [10, 19, 26]. The concern for environmental management gained momentum and emerged as a global agenda in the past few decades [3, 13, 22, 35]. It also gained impetus in the 21st century [3] when organisations increased their sense of pressure to incorporate human resource management functions with environmental management issues [8, 28, 30]. In 2012, the global temperature was approximately 0.85°C, and now it has increased to approximately an average temperature of 1.5°C [21]. This influences national and international organisations to participate and include environmental management issues in their policies, strategies and practices [11, 17, 29]. As international strategies, sustainable development goals 13, 14 and 15 were introduced by the United Nations (UN) as among the agenda 2030 sustainable development goals (SDGs) to ensure global participation in environmental management [7]. Furthermore, the United Nations (UN) has taken steps to ensure environmental management through resolutions and agreements like the Kyoto Protocol of 1997, the Paris Agreement of 2015 and the Glasgow Climate Pact of 2021 [25, 38]. African countries have taken steps in environmental management to adopt a sustainable environment and blue economy strategy [12, 32]. Organisations have been adopting different mechanisms for environmental management, such as green marketing, green accounting and green management [38]. Currently, organisations have expanded their horizon to implement and integrate human resource management functions with environmental management policies. This is termed green human resource management practices, abbreviated as GHRM practices. GHRM practices are implemented through recruitment and selection, training and development, rewards, performance management and employee relations. The implementation of GHRM practices focuses on

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generating employee pro-environmental behaviour that leads to environmental sustainability [34, 36]. Implementing GHRM practices allows the integration of human resource management functions like training, motivation and performance evaluation with environmental management aspects [6, 38]. This draws attention and attracts practitioners and scholars to study the implementation and impacts of green human resource management practices. [5, 9, 16, 31, 38, 41, 43], commented that theoretical studies on the implementation and impacts of GHRM practices have been conducted in developed countries like Europe, Asian countries and the US but are less considerable in developing countries like Tanzania. [3, 24, 28, 44], commented that the implementation of GHRM practices in developing countries, including Tanzania, is still in the infant stage from both theoretical and practical perspectives. Therefore, there is a need to conduct a study to investigate the implementation and impacts of green human resource management (GHRM) practices on employees' pro-environmental behaviour, particularly in tourist hotels in Tanzania, to bridge the gap in the deficiency of the existing literature.

2 Statement of the Problem

Global concerns for environmental management force organisations to integrate human resource management functions with environmental issues [18, 21]. This is because green human resource management practices increase waste management skills, train employees on energy saving and influence employee green behaviour [1]. Moreover, green human resource management (GHRM) practices cultivate employee green knowledge, pro-environmental behaviour and employee green psychology in the organisation. However, environmental problems affect society, governments and organisations [6, 19]. Environmental problems like climate change, global warming, and environmental pollution attract global attention from society, governments, and organisations [10, 14, 26, 36]. For example, in 2012, the global temperature was approximately 0.85°C, and now it has increased to approximately an average temperature of 1.5°C [21]. This influences organisations to participate and include environmental management issues in their policies, strategies and practices. As International strategies, sustainable development goals 13, 14 and 15 were introduced to ensure global participation in environmental management [7]. Furthermore, various mechanisms have been made by the United Nations to show efforts for environmental management, such as the Kyoto Protocol of 1997, the Paris Agreement of 2015 and the Glasgow climate pact of 2021 [26, 37, 38]. African countries, through the umbrella of the African Union, have taken steps for environmental management, such as a sustainable environment and blue economy [30]. Organisations have been adopting different mechanisms for environmental management, such as green marketing, green accounting and green management [38]. Currently, organisations have expanded their horizon to integrate environmental management policies with human resource management functions. All these efforts force organisations to implement GHRM practices in their organisation to ensure organisational competitiveness and sustainability. [24, 44] explained that in developing countries, GHRM practices are a new concept. In this regard, the implementation of GHRM practices is questionable in many organisations, particularly in tourist hotels in Tanzania. Amrutha and Geetha [5] explained

that in the European context, trade unions have a significant influence on environmental management. Therefore, trade unions can act as barriers to implementing GHRM practices if the country has rigid laws. The social exchange theory explains that organisations have to grant opportunity and motivation to employees, particularly through representatives; this will develop a sense of identity that influences pro-environmental behaviour. Furthermore, the literature shows that there is limited literature in developing countries, particularly in Tanzania, which raises this question that needs to be answered. [38], pointed out that the essence of implementing GHRM practices in the organisation is not only to change production, products or services but also to change organisational culture by embedding deep employee value in environment management. [40], explain that the impacts of implementing GHRM practices include a commitment from employees, high production, cost reduction and employee retention, which results in environmental performance. This study is important to be conducted in developing countries, specifically in Tanzania, so as to enrich the existing literature conducted in developing countries, specifically in tourist hotels in Tanzania. In Tanzania, there is no study conducted in tourist hotels regarding to the implementation and impact of GHRM practices for pro-environmental behaviour. This study will be guided by three research questions, namely;

- i. To what extent does implementing green human resource management practices in tourist hotels impact environmental sustainability in Tanzania?
- ii. How do barriers to implementing green human resource management practices in tourist hotels hinder environmental sustainability in Tanzania?

3 Research Methodology

This research will employ an exploratory design, and a qualitative research design will be adopted. Based on a few extant studies [8, 15], the case study design is the most appropriate method to be applied in the study. It allows the exploration of data in which interviews and focus group discussions (FGD) can be used in different cases. Different tourist hotels in Tanzania that stipulate the practice of GHRM in their plans and policies have been chosen as cases. Three regions of Tanzania that have well-known tourist attractions (Dar es Salaam, Arusha, and Zanzibar) (URT, 2022) have been earmarked for this purpose. The study will make use of both primary and secondary data.

Primary data: The study will collect first-hand data directly from the field through interviews and focus group discussions [34, 43]. Relevant employees and HR managers will be requested to take part in the study.

Secondary data will be obtained from literature searches using specific keywords and phrases to tap the most relevant information. Keywords/phrases such as green human resource management, green human resource management practices, green HRM practices, GHRM practices, sustainability of human resource management and environmental sustainability will be used. High-impact factor journals through available electronic databases, including Elsevier, Emerald Insight, Sage Publication, Wiley Online Library, Springer, and Taylor and Francis (online and Routledge will be used for this purpose. The study will also review various documents pertaining to laws,

policies, and regulations and reports from the ILO, UN, UNEP, AU, government and organisations.

Data analysis: Data collected will be analysed qualitatively by using thematic analysis. Suppose required data analysis software like Nvivo or thematic analysis will be applied to aid the analysis process. Prior to data collection, the researcher will seek clearance from the university's ethical committee and also request the required research permit from Tanzanian organisations to conduct the study as appropriate. Ethical consent will also be sought from respondents before collecting data.

4 Description of the Artifact

The artifact of this study is based on the research variable, which is green human resource management GHRM practices. Green human resource management practices include green recruitment and selection, green training and development, green rewards and compensation, green job design and evaluation and green performance management. The implementations of GHRM practices influence environmental sustainability in tourist hotels. Moreover, the implementation of GHRM practices cultivates employees' green behaviours in the organization. Also, GHRM practices encourage and contribute to cultivating employees' green behaviour, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Conceptual Framework

5 Summary of Work done to Date

The study started in November 2023. An intensive literature review has been done to identify the existing gap. A systematic literature review pertaining to the concept of green human resource management practices concept has been conducted. Keywords identified include “green human resource management”, “green human resource management practices”, “green HRM practices”, “GHRM practices”, “sustainability of human resource management” and “environmental sustainability. Approximately more than 100 sources, including journal articles, book chapters, and conference papers, have been reviewed based on the keywords criteria. Journal articles were searched from research databases or publishing companies like Elsevier, Emerald Insight, Sage publication, Wiley Online Library, Springer and Taylor and Francis (online and Routledge).

6 Contribution of the Study

The study expects to contribute to a wider understanding of the existing literature pertaining to green human resource management practices. The findings of the study will enable organisations to have the best option for the appropriate implementation of GHRM practices for environmental sustainability. Furthermore, the study will enlighten governments on the appropriate policies and regulations to be improved to ensure the effective implementation of GHRM practices for the environment.

7 Research Assurance of Transparency

The research will ensure transparency through impartiality and independence during data collection. The researcher will be grounded by positivism, which allows for neutral and providing relevant and trustworthy information [41]. Furthermore, data will be collected from the organisation in which the researcher has no personal interest. The selection of the organisation will be based on scientific justifications, and the researcher will also ensure validity by conducting a pilot study before the actual data collection process. Furthermore, the researcher will apply for research clearance permits from the University of Technology, Mauritius and relevant authorities from the tourism sector in Tanzania.

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Workplace Learning Effectiveness and Internal Service Quality in the Public Sector: Development of an Instrument and Testing of a Predictive Structural Model

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Abstract. The purpose of this study is to develop an instrument of measure for the influence of Human Resource Development on internal service quality in the Public Sector in Mauritius. The study will firstly identify the workplace learning methods which employees perceive as effective for service quality delivery and then identify the perceived influencing factors affecting the achievement of service quality delivery when an employee learns in the workplace. This will be followed by the investigation of the relationship between the influencing factors of workplace learning and service quality delivery and the perceived effectiveness of workplace learning.

The study will be guided by the research question: What are the perceived influencing factors affecting the achievement of service quality delivery when employees learn in the workplace? It is proposed to use the 3 P's model (Presage, Process and Product) by Tynjala, (2013), derived from Biggs (1987) and modified accordingly to suit workplace learning, to answer the research questions. Presage includes learner factors or individual factors and learning context or organizational factors and the product relates to the outcomes of learning, while the process is the means through which employees learn (formal and/or informal methods).

Workplace learning englobes a wide variety of learning activities under formal and informal learning and has common elements: gain in knowledge, skills and attitude. The way individual learn in organisations are influenced by both individual and organizational factors. At individual level: motivation, job satisfaction, reflection, self-efficacy, self-confidence, demographics (age), and at organisational level: team work, work environment, leadership, supervisor support, access to information, communication amongst others will be investigated in relation to the research question.

Internal service quality of employees in the public sector is crucial for the delivery of service quality to external customers. Can this be done without a well-developed human resource? What is the role of learning and development in the achievement of this objective? The research aims to benefit scholars by bringing additional knowledge to the literature, and equip practitioners with appropriate tool to respond to the challenges of the public sector in Mauritius.

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This study will introduce a unique model explaining the relationship between influencing factors and its efficiency and the mediating role of workplace learning to achieve internal service quality. Further this study will be among the few to use multilevel regression analysis for influencing factors of workplace learning at individual and organisational level to cover a sample of 400 employees from 24 Ministries in Mauritius. The development of the model and the testing of the hypothesis will make use of Structural Equation Modeling and ultimately to help bridge the gap between the two fields of study that is Human Resource Development and Internal Service Quality.

1 Background of Research

The main aim of Human Resource Development (HRD) through workplace learning is to maintain the human capital of the organisation up to date and ready to face present and future challenges (TKachenko, Seo & Ardichvili, 2022; Kim, Kwon & Choi, 2024; To and Leung, 2024). HRD is impacted by personal and organisational factors and a good learning climate and a proper mix of formal and informal learning will result in a highly knowledgeable and skilful workforce (Tynjala, 2013; Salcedo, Williams, Elias, Valencia & Perz, 2022). HRD cannot be limited to formal training and development activities to tackle all issues in the organisation, specifically the complex issues in the public sector. With a quality perspective in service delivery, the public sector through their respective administrators should have a different vision regarding the learning taking place in their respective ministries and agencies (Kleefstra, Altan, and Stoffers, 2020). This research focuses on an HRD measure and will study the influence of workplace learning on internal service quality delivery in the public sector in Mauritius.

2 Specific Problem being examined

There is a significant gap that needs consideration as this current study has not yet been established empirically in the literature and in so doing will extend the literature by adding evidence empirically that workplace learning has an impact on internal service quality improvement in the public sector. Further, some evidence suggests that the public sector has specific contextual characteristics that may set it apart from other industries in terms of organisational dynamics. As such, this research will organise all instruments of measures in organisations and will develop and validate a measure for workplace learning for internal service quality in the Public Sector.

The study aims to develop an instrument and testing of a Predictive Structural Model for Human Resource Development, Workplace Learning Effectiveness and Internal Service Quality in the Public Sector. The research questions express the purpose of the study so as to address the research problem. The research is based on the following questions while evaluating the factors influencing the development of an instrument of measure for Human Resource Development for Internal Service Quality delivery.

3 Methodological Approach

The overall objective of the research methodology adopted will be to collect data to help generate a good insight into the phenomenon of workplace learning in the public sector. The population of the public sector is about 75,000 (Statistics Mauritius, 2023) and these include Ministries and Parastatals. In order to focus on main service delivery, only ministries and their respective departments will be taken into consideration and the population is about 50,000 (Statistics Mauritius, 2023) government officers. The expected sample will be about 400 and will be from about 24 Ministries of the Government of Mauritius. Secondary data collection will be done through the literature search of books, journal articles, and online sources amongst others. The research papers and other relevant literature will be scrutinised to inform the researcher on the way an individual learns in organisations, what learning activities the individuals are engaged in and what are the potential influencing factors which affect the choice of these learning activities (Aggarwal, Dhaliwal and Nobi, 2018; Decius, 2019; 2021; 2023; Grosemans, et al., 2020) which will help to set the research questions and ultimately the research hypotheses. The collection of primary data will be done using a mixed-method approach (Rahman and Shiddike, 2020; Molina-Azorin, 2016; Antwi and Hamza, 2015; Molina-Azorin and Fetters, 2019; 2020). An interview will be conducted to gather additional information from managers (Lecat, Raemdonck, Beusaert, and Marz, 2019), and this will be followed by the administration of a questionnaire to sampled employees, online and by hand.

The second phase of this research will be to empirically test the conceptual framework. This will be done by using a quantitative approach to measure the objectives set and to answer the research questions. The quantitative approach will be used together with the qualitative approach for research questions 1 to 5. A mixed method approach will be used for this research, with a qualitative method based on the phenomenological approach together with a quantitative approach based on a post-positivist approach. Interviews will be held with Permanent Secretaries and Head of Departments and questionnaires will be administered to employees. The mixed method approach which makes use of qualitative and quantitative approaches is a possibility to give a better insight into the problem and thereafter the solution of the research questions to the researcher.

A triangulation (Decrop, 1999; Sim and Sharp, 1998; Donato et al., 2017) of the results obtained from each approach will be done to ascertain the data collected. Following a multilevel regression analysis for testing the factors at both the individual and organisational levels, a structural equation modelling will be used to test the hypothesis. There are several methods and methodologies that have been used to research workplace learning (Flemming and Zegwaard, 2018), both quantitative and qualitative.

4 Description of the Artifacts

Workplace learning involves a wide variety of learning activities under formal and informal learning and has common elements such as gain in knowledge, skills, and

attitude. The way individuals learn in organisations is influenced by both individual and organisational factors at the individual level and organisational level and will be investigated in relation to the research questions. The research aims to benefit scholars by bringing additional knowledge to the literature and equipping practitioners with appropriate tools to respond to the challenges of the public sector in Mauritius. This study will introduce a unique model explaining the relationship between influencing factors and the mediating role of workplace learning to achieve internal service quality. Further, this study will be among the few to use multilevel regression analysis for influencing factors of workplace learning at the individual and organisational level to cover a sample of 400 employees from 24 Ministries in Mauritius.

The author presents a synthesis of the current literature on workplace learning guided by the main research question: What are the factors which influence employees learning in the workplace? The psychological theories and the socio-cultural theories inform the development of the theoretical model of the study. It is proposed to use the 3 P's (Presage, Process, Product) model and modified accordingly to suit workplace learning. Presage includes learner factors or individual factors and learning context or organisational factors and the product relates to the outcomes of learning, while the process consists of the means through which employees learn; either through formal or informal learning or through a combination of both. Workplace learning involves a wide variety of learning activities under formal and informal learning and has common elements such as gain in knowledge, skills, and attitude. The way individuals learn in organisations is influenced by both personal and organisational factors. It is worth noting that many studies have focused on either personal factors or organisational factors, as influencing factors for the adoption of workplace learning, but very few have considered both types of factors in one study. The study reveals that personal factors such as reflection, task uncertainty, motivation, promotion opportunities, organisational commitment, job satisfaction, self-efficacy, and proactivity while organisational factors such as job characteristics, organisational and top management support, learning climate, and leadership are among the most influential factors which trigger the effectiveness of workplace learning in an organisation. Based on the above, the authors will evaluate the potential predictors and will propose a conceptual model for understanding workplace learning adoption using personal and organisational factors.

5 Expected Contribution of the Work

The literature suggests that there is some link between workplace learning and internal service quality (Tynjala, 2008; 2013). The aim is to develop a model and to identify the possible relationships between workplace learning and internal service quality. This study will introduce a unique model explaining the relationship between the influencing factors of workplace learning and its efficiency and its mediating role on internal service quality (Uhunoma, et al., 2021). The current study will be one of the few studies that will empirically relate learning factors, learning efficiency, and the outcomes of internal service quality while employees are in the process of learning in the workplace. It will offer a classification of the factors that lead to workplace learning efficiency and

internal service quality (Otoo et al., 2018). This research will attempt to pave the way for the development of a measure for HRD for internal service quality in the public sector and, as such will add to the existing literature by emphasizing the combination of formal and informal workplace learning in a distinctive context such as the public sector in which learning takes place (Kusaila, 2019). The use of structural equation modelling to bridge the gap between the two fields of research: Human Resource Development and Internal Service Quality.

6 Plan to assure Research Transparency

In this particular research like most research, the data collection will be primarily from human participants. We need to ensure that all approval is obtained from an ethical point of view before conducting the survey and distribution of questionnaires (Fleming, 2018), which includes the willingness of the individual to participate in the survey. Relevant permission will be sought from public bodies as and when required.

7 Summary

This research has main objective to develop an instrument of measure for HRD for internal service quality in public sector organisations. The study will allow the author and other researchers to have a better understanding of:

- i. the personal and organisational factors which influence the adoption of workplace learning;
- ii. the learning activities preferred by individuals in the workplace,
- iii. the relationship between workplace learning and internal service quality.

Further, the study will add to existing literature by considering both formal and informal workplace learning in one study; and will make use of structural equation modelling to test the hypothesis.

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Inclusive Service Experiences: Emotions and Customer Satisfaction in the Context of Disability

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Abstract. This paper explores the emotional impact of interactions with disabled employees on customer satisfaction within service environments. It reviews existing literature on service quality and customer satisfaction, highlighting the SERVQUAL model and its dimensions. The study addresses the research gap regarding the influence of disabled employees on customer satisfaction, particularly in the Mauritian context. Through a meta-analysis and surveys, the paper aims to understand how emotional reactions triggered by these interactions affect customer satisfaction, advocating for disability inclusion in the workplace. This methodological approach allows a comprehensive understanding of the subject, and serves as a solid foundation for subsequent phases of the research. Phases, which will take the form of another paper and the final doctoral paper by the end of next year

Keywords: Disability Inclusion, Inclusive Workplace, Customer Satisfaction, Service Quality

1 Introduction

In recent years, many researchers have focused on the effect of factors such as waiting time, customer loyalty [5], music and sound effects, spatial environment, employee politeness, service quality, self-service technologies [9,13] presence of employees on the floor, or empathy on customer satisfaction. Yet, despite the high volume of investigations about customer satisfaction, there is clearly a significant gap regarding the influence of employees with disabilities on customer satisfaction. One of the main reasons that could explain this research gap may be a hypothetical lack of commitment from developed countries to promote disability inclusion in the workplace or the persistently high unemployment rates among people with disabilities [3].

The focus of this paper aims at further understanding and identifying the factors that are considered essential by different scholars to build a memorable customer experience. The objective is to review existing research on customer satisfaction, specifically the impact of emotional reactions caused by interactions with disabled employees in the workplace. Taking Mauritius as a background for the study, this research attempts to answer the following questions: Could the inclusion of disabled persons in the

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workplace environment trigger emotional reactions, referred to as affective events, that would affect customer satisfaction? If yes, should disabled persons not be treated as an asset in a Society 5.0, and should our society not promote more aggressively the integration of all individuals in a Society 5.0? Mauritius also suffers from the restricted presence of persons with disabilities in the workplace environment.

2 Literature Review

2.1 The intricate relationship between Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is strongly linked to the quality of service, which is evaluated by how well service delivered aligns with customer expectations. The quality of service is commonly evaluated by the degree to which an institution fulfills or surpasses the expectations of its customers, acting as a barometer for customer satisfaction. Therefore, customers are disposed to report greater satisfaction when they sense that the services provider caters to surpass their expectations. Conversely, research has revealed that individuals often judge a service to be substandard if it includes negative aspects such as prolonged waiting times, complicated procedures, unfulfilled promises, or discourteous interactions.

A review of the literature highlighted the strong connection between these concepts and it resulted in the research of Parasuraman et al [21] who introduced the SERVQUAL model. This model was tested in different service environment and this framework has been applied in service setting such as educational institutions [43]. This validated the assumption that SERVQUAL is an effective tool for assessing service quality and, consequently, customer satisfaction within service-oriented organizations. Supporting this view, studies conducted in sectors like healthcare, banking, hospitality, and education illustrate its applicability.

The SERVQUAL model comprises five dimensions: Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Empathy [21]. Tangibility pertains to the physical aspects of the service environment such as facilities, equipment, and the visual presentation of staff. Reliability involves a company's ability to honor its commitments. Responsiveness is the organization's readiness and swiftness in addressing customer inquiries. Assurance evaluates the knowledge and skill of the staff, along with the confidence and trust they instill in customers. Empathy measures how well a company grasps the distinct needs of its customers

Fig. 1. Disabled population by island and sex, 2000 and 2011 Population Censuses

2.2 Service Quality Measurement: A Comparative Analysis of Nordic and American Perspectives and Its Adaptation to the Mauritian Culture

The Nordic and American perspectives offer opposing approaches for assessing service quality. The former concentrates on the functional and technical aspects of service quality, as highlighted by Daniel and Berinyuy [8], while the latter highlights customer perceptions of service interactions, focusing on elements like reliability, responsiveness, empathy, assurance, and tangibles [21]. Literature reviews suggest that the American perspective aligns more closely with Mauritian culture. This is supported by studies such as Vencataya et al [39], which validated the SERVQUAL model's effectiveness in evaluating the banking sector's service quality in Mauritius, emphasizing the importance of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibles.

Similarly, Prayag [27] applied the SERVQUAL framework to measure international tourists' service quality perceptions at Air Mauritius, further affirming that the American perspective's relevance in Mauritius. Additional research in the public sector [28] and the restaurant industry by [28] also validated the suitability of the SERVQUAL dimensions within the Mauritian context, demonstrating their influence on customer satisfaction and behavioral intentions. All these studies reinforce the compatibility of the American perspective's SERVQUAL dimensions with the service quality measurement in Mauritius.

2.3 The Role of Emotional Engagement in service environment

A review of the literature, revealed that an emotion can be defined as a complex psychological state including a variety of feelings, thoughts, and physiological changes. The distinction between surprise and emotions lies in the fact that emotions are immediate responses to event, stimuli, or situations that significantly influence human behavior and experience. Whereas Surprise is often defined as an emotional or cognitive response to an unexpected or unexplained event. According to research by Rebecca Maguire and Phil Maguire [17], surprise can manifest in three ways: subjectively (as a feeling), physiologically and behaviorally.

Literature review extensively documented on emotional contagion and it indicates that emotional contagion often occurs between service providers and customers [2]. Additionally, numerous studies have been undertaken to determine whether emotions serve as a criterion for achieving customer satisfaction. Research in service marketing [33] and workplace emotions demonstrates that emotions are essential and exert a considerable impact within the service sector. Extensive research on emotions and emotional contagion has hypothesized that emotional contagion influences the behaviors of both employees and customers [11]. It has been revealed that emotions are crucial in creating positive customer experiences and behaviors in the service environment.

2.4 Disability Demographics and Trends in Mauritius: A Statistical Overview

As shown in FAs at 31 December 2023, it was estimated that the population of the Republic of Mauritius is amounted to 1,260,379 [35], with a net decrease of 817 from previous year’s figure. Disability affects a significant segment of the population, with approximately 1 in 20 individuals identified as having a disability [34], totaling 59,868 people as shown in Figure 2.

Island	2000			2011		
	Male	Female	Both Sexes	Male	Female	Both Sexes
Island of Mauritius	20,034	19,606	39,640	28,010	29,746	57,756
Island of Rodrigues	542	608	1,150	977	1,135	2,112
Republic of Mauritius	20,576	20,214	40,790	28,987	30,881	59,868

Fig. 2. Disabled population by island and sex, 2000 and 2011 Population Censuses.
Source: Statistics of Mauritius

The Census Disability Analytical Report [34] is one of the most documented reports undertaken in Mauritius. This report is based on data collected for the 2011 Housing and Population Census, which is the 18th census for the Island of Mauritius and the 8th for the Island of Rodrigues. The aim of such report and census is to aid policymakers and governmental bodies in developing policies for the inclusion of disabled persons. The volume of 59,868 disabled persons represents approximately 1 in 20 people in Mauritius, based on the population rate for year 2011 [34], which is a considerable ratio for a small country as Mauritius. This volume increase to 86,607, representing approximately 1 in 14 people in Mauritius for year 2022 [35]. This supported the objective of undertaking such research in the Mauritian context to aid in the societal inclusion of persons with a disability. The amount of working disabled population represents 8,435 employed disabled persons [34], from which 70% are men and 30% are women. As stated above in the review of the literature, working is crucial to attain financial independence and societal inclusion. Therefore, exploring such social phenomenon is valuable as research. Additionally, about 98% of the disabled population lives in private households [34], which means that 98% of the disabled person or the majority are living in a familial context. On the other hand, around 1,160 disabled persons live in institutions, with 67% being aged 60 and above. Therefore, we can deduce that these 1,160 have limited mobility and cannot be introduced to a workplace environment. In the 2011 census, during the survey participants were requested to simply respond to a “yes” or “no” response to the question: “does this person have any difficulty in performing daily life activities which are considered normal for his/her age”. The data gathered enables to identify the above categories of impairment as shown in Figure 3.

Daily life activity	Impairment category
A Seeing even if wearing glasses	EYE
B Hearing even if using a hearing aid	EAR
C Walking or climbing stairs	MTION
D Remembering, concentrating or acquiring education and learning	LEARN
E Looking after oneself with regard to feeding, personal care and hygiene	PERSONAL CARE
F Speaking and talking	SPEECH
G Manual activities such as gripping and holding	MANU
H Disturbances of behaviour, including antisocial behaviour, maladjustment, and liability to self-injury	BEHAVIOUR

Source: 2011 Housing and Population Census.

Fig. 3. Daily life activities and impairment categories, listed as per the 2011 Housing and Population Census

The Social Protection and Disability in Mauritius Report [7] reported some issues in the 2011 Housing and Population Census, although an effort was made to adopt international standards of measuring disability prevalence. First, asking people to simply answer "yes" or "no" to whether they have a disability is too vast. It misses to identify people with ongoing health issues or mental illnesses. Secondly, the methodology can cause older people to underestimate their disabilities. Since many disabilities are common in older age, people might think their condition is just normal aging and say "no" when asked if they have a disability. The Mauritian context is also in line with the global trends where disability prevalence tend to increase sharply with age, with almost a third of people over 75 years reporting a disability, this trend is illustrated in Figure 4. The review of the existing literature in the Mauritian context demonstrate that the most common disability is related to mobility, the most prevalent being “walking or climbing stairs”, which represents approximately 30% of disabled persons followed by “seeing” difficulties amounted to 15%. The different disability prevalence by Age and broad type of disability are illustrated in Figure 5.

Source: Statistics of Mauritius

Fig. 4. Disability prevalence by Age group, 2000 and 2011 Population Censuses

Fig. 5. Disability prevalence by Age group and broad type of disability, 2011 Population Census

Some of the societal indicators are access to education, access to work or economic independence. Referring to educational barometer, that educational access for disabled persons has improved, in 2011 80% having attended school compared to 65% in 2000 [34]. This is still very low compares to the overall population where the educational level is of approximatively 80 to 90 % for Primary/Secondary education and 50 % for Tertiary education [34]. A comparison of the educational attainment is shown in Figure

6, where a comparison is made between the overall population and the population with disabilities this is highlighted in red in the following figure. Additionally, about 2,650 disabled persons are currently attending or have attended Special Education Needs schools [34]. Coming to the economic independence of disabled persons, it was shown that economic activity among the disabled population increased from 12.5% in 2000 to 16.7% in 2011, but remains significantly lower than the 58.7% for the overall [34]. The sectors where the most disabled person are employed is the manufacturing sector where 18.2% of the disabled population is employed, followed by the wholesale and retail trade: 14.1%, and agriculture: 12.8% [34]. This census also demonstrated that disabled individuals are often engaged in elementary occupations, which represents 24.7% of the jobs and craft-related trades 20.1%. The following shows a comparison of the census made in the Year 2000 against the Census undertaken in 2011:

Source: Statistics Mauritius

Educational attainment	<i>(i) Disabled population</i>			<i>(ii) Overall population</i>		
	2011			2011		
	Male	Female	Both Sexes	Male	Female	Both Sexes
Nil and pre-primary	13.7	31.1	22.6	6.8	11.0	9.0
Primary	49.1	46.0	47.5	35.4	36.6	36.0
Std I-VI but not passed CPE	37.1	35.0	36.0	27.2	27.2	27.2
Passed CPE	12.1	11.0	11.5	8.2	9.4	8.8
Secondary	29.7	18.1	23.7	51.9	48.5	50.2
Form I-V but not passed SC	18.8	11.5	15.1	28.3	25.1	26.7
Passed SC or HSC	10.9	6.6	8.7	21.6	23.4	23.5
University degree or equivalent	1.3	0.6	0.9	4.4	3.1	3.8
Specialised school for the Disabled	5.5	3.4	4.4			
Other & not stated ¹⁾	0.7	0.8	0.8	1.4	0.8	1.1
Total	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0

Fig. 6. Comparison of Education level Disabled population vs Overall Population, 2011 Population Census

Fig. 7. Activity rate (%) of the disabled and the overall population aged 16 and above, 2011
Population Census

According to the latest census, there were 55,614 disabled individuals aged 16 and older. Out of these, 9,299 were engaged in work or job-seeking, while 46,071 were not participating in the labor force [34]. This translates to 16.7% of disabled people being economically active and 82.8% economically inactive, this is shown in Figure 7 above. Of those actively involved, 90.7% were employed, leaving 9.3% unemployed. The main reasons for inactivity among the disabled were their disability itself (46.8%), retirement (25.9%), and household responsibilities (23%) [34]. The overall activity rate for disabled individuals was significantly lower, three times less than that of the general population, with the disparity being even more pronounced among disabled women [34].

3 Research methodology

3.1 Research Strategy

This chapter explains the research design and methodology used in this meta-analysis, which aims to systematically review existing research on customer satisfaction, more specifically the impact of emotional reactions caused by interactions with disabled employees on the subject. The integration of existing findings from multiple studies provides a comprehensive insights about service quality and thus customer satisfaction.

Meta-analysis is considered to be a well-established method in social sciences for conducting research findings across different studies to draw more generalizable conclusions [10]. This research method is a consolidation of the results of numerous small studies to provide a clearer picture and trends, this would be a valuable contribution in examining the impacts of emotional reactions on customer satisfaction. Along with the Meta-analysis, the research methodology employed a mixed method where a pilot testing of a survey will be made with participants, the number of participant will be calculated on Rao soft website.

3.2 Search Strategy

The purpose of this research is to investigate the emotional impact generated by interacting with disabled persons in a service environment and to address the gap in current literature; namely the influence of such interactions on customer satisfaction. To attain this goal, a clearly defined research strategy was established. The foundation of this strategy is constructed on a comprehensive empirical literature review by using Scopus and other source of data such as EBSCO Information, Open Journal Taylor and Francis, Elsevier, Mendeley, ResearchGate, and ProQues.

The primary database used for the literature search was Scopus, this platform provide a comprehensive coverage of peer-reviewed journals and conference papers. As stated above to support the finding, additional data sources were used to ensure a broad search. The use of multiple databases is consistent with recommendations by Bramer et al.

(2017), who emphasize the importance of comprehensive database searching in systematic reviews.

This study adopts a constructivist paradigm, which advances that knowledge is constructed by individuals through their subjective experiences and interactions within social contexts. Data for this phase of the study will be collected using a questionnaire based on the results obtained during the pilot testing of our survey. This pilot testing will inform a more comprehensive subsequent study, which will be discussed in the limitations and further research section of this paper. The data collected will be analyzed on SPSS and Microsoft Excel.

3.3 Methodology: Integrating Meta-Analysis into Longitudinal Research

Search Terms.

To identify the desired papers, the search was conducted using a combination of key terms designed to capture the relevant literature. The key terms used were; Customer Satisfaction, Emotion and Disability Inclusion. Booth [4] supports this technique, where he highlighted the importance of selecting appropriate keywords and search terms to ensure that a systematic reviews and meta-analyses is are conducted. The first step resulted in an initial search substantial number of documents across the key terms; Customer Satisfaction 74,174 documents, Emotion 366,013 documents and Disability Inclusion 24,614 documents.

Filtering Criteria.

A filtering strategy was used to limit the initial search results and ensure that only relevant and quality of the documents are kept. The filtering criteria applied are Year, Document Type, Publication Stage, Language, Source Type and Access.

To ensure that this paper reflects current practices and attitudes, the main focus was on contemporary research [31]. The search was limited to documents published between the years 2000 and 2024. Additionally, only articles, conference papers, and reviews were included to ensure the inclusion of peer-reviewed and fundamental research. This second filtering is in line with practices recommended by the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions [12]. To ensure reliability and completeness of the data gathered, this paper has taken into consideration only papers at the final publication stage, and has excluded drafts and in-progress research [19]. To adhere to the Mauritian context, only documents published in English were considered to maintain consistency in language and interpretation, which is a common practice in systematic reviews [30]. The source of data gathered included journals, conference proceedings, trade journals, book series, and books to encompass a wide range of academic and professional publications. Finally, for convenience purposes and ensure that the studies were readily available for detailed analysis, only open-access documents were included [24]. After applying these filtering criteria, 5,474 documents were identified as potentially relevant. This still represented a considerable number of papers. Therefore an additional filtering technique was applied.

Data Extraction and Initial Filtering.

The 5,474 documents was exported in excel format, containing essential information. This dataset served as the basis for further filtering and analysis. The dataset was further filtered in Excel based on an analysis of the title and connections to key terms such as "SERVQUAL," "Satisfaction," "Frontline Employees," and "Service Quality" were identified. An additional column was created and named as "Theme", where key terms were added to identify the field of research or Theory explored. The use of Excel for data management in systematic reviews is supported by McKeown et al. [18]. After this filtering step, 1,428 documents remained for further analysis. A detailed analysis of the titles was made again, and an additional analysis criteria which is the abstracts of the 1,428 documents. This process involved two independent review to ensure objectivity and consistency, which is a standard practice in systematic reviews to reduce bias [12]. The title and abstract analysis resulted in a refined set of 98 documents. A second filter was applied to the initial 5,474 documents using additional criteria, filtering by using keywords such as "Customer Satisfaction," "Service Quality," "Service Environment," "Satisfaction," "Quality of Service," "Quality," "SERVQUAL," "Customer Service Quality," and "Perceived Quality." This filtering step identified 22 additional documents. The final dataset for analysis consisted of the 98 documents from the first filter and the 22 documents from the second filter, making a total of 120 documents. These documents were analyzed to identify trends and patterns relevant to the hypothesis question. The steps employed are summarized hereunder in Figure 8

Fig. 8. Illustration of Data extraction and Analysis

3.4 Customer Satisfaction Scopus Data Extraction Analysis- Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Starting with the Customer Satisfaction variable, this search enables us to identify 74,174 documents related to customer satisfaction, the Yearly publication pattern is shown in Figure 9. The interest in the customer satisfaction dimension began in the year 2000, with 899 research papers dedicated to Customer Satisfaction. The most promising years were 2004 and 2005, during which a total of 10,302 research papers were found. Most of the research was conducted in the United States, totaling 14,931 studies, as illustrated below. In the Mauritian context, only 31 research papers were found, highlighting a significant research gap in the literature. This gap is further underscored when grouping by continents, revealing a ratio of 51 research papers per country in Africa and 7 research papers per country in Central America. This estimation suggests that approximately 51 research papers were produced across the 41 African countries where research was conducted, and an average of 7 research papers per country in Central America. For the remaining papers, the country of origin was not defined. The trend by

country is illustrated in Figure 10 as shown hereunder. The same analysis was conducted for Emotion and Disability inclusion.

Fig. 9. Elsevier Scopus Illustration of Paper drafter by Year _Customer Satisfaction

Fig. 10. Elsevier Scopus Illustration of Paper drafter by Country _Customer Satisfaction

3.5 Emotion Scopus Data Extraction Analysis-- Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

For the Emotions variable, this search enables us to identify 74,174 documents related to emotions. The interest in the emotions dimension started in the year 1970, with 499 research papers dedicated to emotions. The most promising years were 2022 and 2023, during which a total of 62,958 research papers were found. Most of the research was conducted in the United States, totaling 107,867 studies, as illustrated below. In the Mauritian context, only 22 research papers were found, indicating a research gap in the literature. The evolution by year and country is shown in Figure 11 and Figure 12 respectively.

Fig. 11. Elsevier Scopus Illustration of Paper drafter by Year _Emotions

Fig. 12. Elsevier Scopus Illustration of Paper drafter by Country _Emotions

3.6 Disability Inclusion Scopus Data Extraction Analysis-- Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Disability inclusion is another important variable. This search enables us to identify 24,621 documents related to disability inclusion. The interest in the disability inclusion dimension started in the year 2015, with 1,059 research papers dedicated to disability inclusion, as illustrated in Figure 13. The most promising years were from 2021 to 2023, during which a total of 7,284 research papers were found. Most of the research was conducted in the United States, totaling 7,148 studies, as illustrated below. In the Mauritian context, only 3 research papers were found, highlighting a significant research gap in the literature. This gap is also confirmed when grouping by continents, where it is noted that African countries produced only 1,192 research papers, the lowest volume compared to other continent The publication by country is shown in Figure 14.

Fig. 13. Elsevier Scopus Illustration of Paper drafter by Year_ Disability Inclusion

Fig. 14. Elsevier Scopus Illustration of Paper drafter by Country_ Disability Inclusion

3.7 Database Construction

After identifying the above documents, the filtering process explained in the Methodology section was applied. This process, described in 'Step 2' of Figure 8, reduced the initial dataset to 99 documents somewhat related to the research field. From this dataset of 99 documents, a manual verification was conducted by analyzing the abstracts, methodologies, analyses, and findings of the documents. This enabled us to identify 38 documents closely related to SERVQUAL or the emotional dimensions of our research

3.8 Methodology: Integrating Pilot Surveys into Longitudinal Research

In the sphere of empirical research, robust methodologies are crucial not only for the accuracy of findings but also for planning and execution of studies over extended periods. As stated above this paper is part of a longitudinal research on Customer Satisfaction and Disability inclusion in the Mauritian Context. This paper delves into the comprehensive empirical review and methodology, grounded on the integration of pilot surveys as a key component alongside meta-analytical techniques. This two-research tool would contribute significantly for the drafting of the literature and methodology chapter

of the final research paper. The use of such methodology technique is supported by the research undertaken by The 1970 British Cohort Study where they tracked the lives of 17,000 individuals born in the United Kingdom since their birth and the Harvard Study of Adult Development, a renowned longitudinal study spanning over 80 years, has focused on the physical and mental health of Boston men.

3.9 Meta-Analysis: Establishing the Foundation.

The Meta-analysis undertaken in this research serves as the foundation of our research methodology; it provides a systematic review of existing literature and establishing the study's objectives. By exploring data from different sources, meta-analysis allows us to draw general conclusions and identify trends across diverse studies, which can be used by the managerial professionals in the service industry. This methodological approach allows a comprehensive understanding of the subject, and serves as a solid foundation for subsequent phases of the research. Phases, which will take the form of another paper and the final doctoral paper by the end of next year.

3.10 Survey Methodology: The Role of Pilot Testing

Along with the meta-analysis, our research methodology includes a primary data collection through surveys. Primary collection of data will be only a pilot survey which would be used as a consolidation and foundation for the final survey undertaken by end of next year. This survey will offer invaluable insights into the attitudes, behaviors, and perceptions of participants directly related to our research questions and would be a confirmation or rejection of the conclusion made during our meta-analysis. Additionally, the approach of conducting a pilot testing, is a crucial phase aimed at cleansing the survey instruments prior to full-scale implementation. An empirical review of the literature revealed that various researchers used the polling method in the form of questionnaires [14].

In 2023, the population of the Republic of Mauritius stood at 1,260,379 comprising 622,647 males and 637,732 females [35]. The working population is estimated to be 1,015,300; the estimates refer to the Mauritian population aged 16 years and above. The age distribution of the Mauritian population is shown in Figure 14.

Source: Statistics Mauritius

Age group (Years)	1 July 2022			1 July 2023		
	Male	Female	Both sexes	Male	Female	Both sexes
0	6,114	6,110	12,224	6,263	6,091	12,354
1 - 4	26,428	25,423	51,851	25,886	25,189	51,075
5 - 9	33,613	32,176	65,789	33,158	31,789	64,947
10 - 14	38,275	37,699	75,974	37,077	36,233	73,310
15 - 19	46,606	44,957	91,563	45,044	43,415	88,459
20 - 29	97,276	95,021	192,297	96,691	94,176	190,867
30 - 39	88,253	85,241	173,494	88,943	86,097	175,040
40 - 49	92,511	90,067	182,578	93,106	90,696	183,802
50 - 59	85,332	86,785	172,117	83,317	84,663	167,980
60-64	37,883	41,429	79,312	38,808	42,358	81,166
65+	71,496	93,554	165,050	74,524	97,243	171,767
All ages	623,787	638,462	1,262,249	622,817	637,950	1,260,767

¹ based on 2011 Population Census data adjusted for underenumeration of children
² excluding Agalega and St Brandon

Fig. 15. Age distribution of population – Estimated resident population (1) by broad age group and sex- Republic of Mauritius (2), 1 July 2022 and 1 July 2023

For a targeted population of 1,015,300 the sample size is 34 with a confidence level of 87% and a confidence interval of 13% [29]. For my research, there is an absence of a sampling frame. Therefore, the sample selection will be based on a convenience sampling approach [38], which is a non-probability sampling method. To ensure that the sampling size of 34 is attained, the snowball sampling [37] will be used to help in addressing the questionnaires to individuals who were involved in transacting in a service environment, the same sampling method that will be used in future research papers by end of next year.

3.11 Pilot Survey Design and Implementation

The pilot survey is designed to validate and enhance the reliability of the final survey instrument. It will consist of five sections that will collect and measure pertinent factors and variables. Factors and variables that are all important for the purpose of this paper. The five sections are Customer Satisfaction, Emotional Reactions, and Stereotyping, Types of Disability and Demographic factors. The questionnaire will consist on questions using a 7 Linkert scale for measurement, as used in the research of Yen-Lun Su [36]. A research on Customer Satisfaction measurement practices in Taiwan Hotels. The questionnaire will consist of 19 questions to measure Customer Satisfaction, Emotional Reactions, stereotyping and Types of Disability and 4 questions on the demographic factors. The questionnaire will be designed by utilizing Google Forms as the platform for data collection,

The reason of having a pilot phase is to have continuous feedback from participants. This will enable improvements to the survey design in the two additional papers that would follow this present one. Any refining of wording, response options, or structure would be noted and this will help to minimize ambiguity and enhance clarity. By addressing potential anomalies this paper will aid in fortifying the integrity of the research during this longitudinal study.

Therefore, beyond the immediate role in this research paper, the pilot survey holds broader implications. It serves as a preparatory stage for subsequent publications and a doctoral thesis submission. The rigor in the research strategy and methodology enhances the credibility of the current study but also upcoming publication or research.

4 Hypothesis Construction

From this meta-analysis, we have been able to clearly establish what is our dependent variables, independent variables and mediating variable. Based on the purpose of this research, which is to understand if an emotional reaction caused by the interaction with a disabled employee has an effect on customer satisfaction, we have been able to identify the following variables:

1. Independent Variable (IV): Emotional Reaction: This is the variable that we will be manipulating as part of this research. Based an empirical review of the literature, emotions identified Anger, Fear, Joy, Love, Sadness, And Surprise [20].
2. Dependent Variable (DV): Customer Satisfaction: This is the outcome variable that this paper is interested in measuring. It reflects how satisfied customers feel after their interaction with the disabled employee.
3. Mediating Variable: In the context of this paper, mediator would also be taken into consideration and an assessment of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable will be made. Possible mediators could include:
 - Demographic factors of customer: Previous research shows that demographic factors could have an impact on emotional evaluation and processing. Some of such demographic factors are age or education level [6, 15, 23].
 - Customer's prior attitudes towards disability: Customer familiarity to disability could affect the dependent and independent variable (referred to personal disposition).
 - Customer's prior emotions

4.1 Hypothetical Relationships:

Hypothesis 1: Service quality has a significant direct effect on customer satisfaction in a disability inclusion context. The mediators are the 5 elements of SERVQUAL model; namely tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy. The hypothesis of our experiment is based on the following research and theories: Shiau et al. [32] have demonstrated that tangibles are closely related to high service quality. For the Assurance dimension, Zhou [44] found that reliability and assurance are factors that influence the most customer satisfaction in the Chinese banking sector. Finally, [21], demonstrated that empathy dimension is a good service quality indicator, service quality that affect

Hypothesis 2: Higher levels of positive emotional reactions towards a disabled employee lead to increased customer satisfaction. The mediating factor will be the perceived emotional reaction of participants. This hypothesis is based on the findings of Wegge et al [41] who shows evidence of a relationship between positive and negative affect and satisfaction

Hypothesis 3: Higher levels of negative emotional reactions towards a disabled employee lead to increased customer satisfaction. The mediator would be the perceived emotional reaction of participants. Payne and Cooper [22] has shown that specific events can trigger discrete emotions such as anger, guilt, envy, anxiety or disgust, and the later can have different consequence or reaction

Hypothesis 4: Customer familiarity to disability dimension or Gender has a significant direct effect on customer satisfaction in a disability inclusion context. The mediator would be analyzing and measuring the personal Disposition of customer.

Hypothesis 5: Gender has a significant direct effect on stereotyping in the context of disability inclusion. The mediator would be analyzing and measuring the warmth and competence evaluation.

The identification of these different variables provide a conceptual framework to aid in the understanding of how emotional reactions influence customer satisfaction in the context of interacting with a disabled employee. The conceptual framework is illustrated hereunder:

4.2 Conceptual Framework

This paper is based on the following conceptual framework, it investigates whether an event triggers an emotional reaction in human beings that affect customer satisfaction and if mediating factors such as demographic factors have an effect on the emotional reaction. Figure 15 is an illustration of the conceptual framework of this research paper.

Fig 15: Conceptual Framework of the Research Paper

5 Analysis and Interpretation

The dataset analyzed, comprises responses related to a survey aimed at understanding the emotional reactions and customer satisfaction when served by employees with disabilities. The survey collected information from 86 participants and focuses on their emotions, perceived service quality [21], demographic details, and personal connections to individuals with disabilities.

6 Descriptive Statistics and Data Analysis

The sample is made up of diverse demographic groups with varying emotional reactions and perceptions of service quality. This enables us to have different participants with similarities and differences and avoid bias in the sample construction. The sample was assembled randomly, aiming to ensure representativeness and avoid bias. It consists of 53 female participants (61.6%), 32 male participants (37.2%), and in one case, the gender type was not specified (1.2%). Details were also collected concerning the age groups, as literature has shown that ‘people go from lower to higher levels of moral thinking as they get older. The highest age group in our sample is the 35–44 age group, representing 39 participants (45.3%). This is followed by the 45–54 age group, where it was observed that 19 participants selected this age group (22.1%). Additionally, 17 participants stated that they are aged between 25 and 34 (19.8%), while the number of participants aged between 55 and 64 represents 8.1% of the total. The 18–24 age group comprises 4.7%. Importantly, no participants are in the age group under 18 years or 65 and above. Data were also collected to understand income patterns among participants, this enables to better illustrate the demographic profile of the participants. Notably, 24.4% of participants earned an income between MUR 15,000 and MUR 29,999, followed by 22.1% in the group earning MUR 45,000 to MUR 59,999. The third-largest category consisted of participants earning MUR 30,000 to MUR 44,999 (20.9%). Additionally, 32.6% of the sample fell into other income groups: 10 participants in the MUR 60,000–MUR 74,999 range and a similar proportion for MUR 75,000 or more. Ethical considerations require us to provide participants with the option not to disclose their income group, this applies for seven participants. Another important consideration, since it affects the personal disposition of participants, they were asked if they have a close relative with a disability, 50 participants replied “YES” and 36 participants replied “NO”.

Before starting the survey, participants were asked to specify the emotion that best described their current emotional state. As shown in the Table 1, 36% of the participants stated that “Surprise” was the emotion that best described their emotional state before undertaking the questionnaire, followed by “Joy,” felt by 26% of the participants. Another recurrent emotional state is “Love,” which represents 9%, and 12% of the participants were unable to identify their perceived emotional state. Meanwhile, 78% of the participants experienced a change in emotion when comparing their emotions at the start and when they began to imagine an interaction with a disabled employee. At the end of the questionnaire, participants were asked again to describe their emotional state

after imagining different scenarios involving employees with disabilities. As shown in Table 1, 78% of the participants experienced a change in their emotional state related to the involvement of employees with disabilities. Table 2 shows the different emotional state at the end of the questionnaire.

Table 1. Emotional States and Changes in Emotional States

Which of the following emotions best describes your current emotional state while taking this questionnaire	Total
Curiosity	4
Fear	1
Hopeful.	1
Joy	22
Love	8
Neutral	10
Sadness	5
Stressed	2
Surprise	31
Tired	2
Grand Total	86

Emotion at Start V/S Emotion at End	Percentage	Number of Participants
Change	78	67
No Change	22	19

Table 2. Emotional States at end of experiment

Imagine that you are being served by a disabled person in a service environment, which of the following emotions best describes your emotional state after such experience?	%
Surprise	29.07%
Love	26.74%
Joy	19.77%
Other (If other , please specify in next question)	13.95%
Sadness	10.47%
Grand Total	100.00%

Understanding the reasons for such a change is crucial; therefore, participants were asked about possible reasons explaining this shift in emotional states. The most common reason given was “Admiration for the determination” of disabled employees, representing 21%. This was followed by “Pride” associated with observing an inclusive society, accounting for 19%. And finally “Surprise” associated to this unusual affective event represent 14 % following by 9 % of the participant who answered that the “recognition” that the society shows to the potential of disabled persons causes this shift in emotional state. Table 3 illustrates the different reasons triggering this emotional change

Inclusive Service Experiences: Emotions and Customer Satisfaction

Table 3. Sentiment Analysis on what causes emotional change related to disability inclusion in the workplace

Reasons Triggering Change in Emotion	
	%
Admiration for determination	20.9
Pride in inclusivity	18.6
Surprise	14.0
Recognizing potential	9.3
Others	37.2
Total	100

During the literature, a number of researchers have demonstrated that disabled employees are considered as being friendly but not competent. This phenomenon is referred as stereotyping. To analyze this hypothesis two questions focused on the warmth and competence dimensions of disabled employees. As illustrated hereunder, 66.3 % of the participant associated disabled employees to friendliness (43 % stated that they are friendly and 23.3% as somewhat friendly). For the competence dimension, 61.7% of the participant stated that they see disabled person as competent and 86 % of the participants as capable. Figure 16 illustrates the results related to the warmth dimension, while Figure 17 illustrates the competence dimension.

Fig. 16. Stereotype –Warmth Dimensions

Fig. 17. Stereotype –Competence Dimensions

To better understand the reaction of participants toward different types of disability, further analysis was conducted. The data in Table 3 reveals customer attitudes towards service quality when interacting with employees with disabilities. It indicates that the majority of customers feel neutral to positive when served by individuals with physical disabilities, with 43.02% expressing a neutral stance and 15.12% perceiving it somewhat positively. In cases of visual impairment, 31.40% of customers remained neutral, while 25.58% had a somewhat positive perception. Hearing impairment saw a similar distribution, with 31.40% neutral and 23.26% somewhat positive responses. Intellectual/Mental disabilities presented a more diverse response, yet 29.07% of customers were neutral, and 25.58% viewed the interaction somewhat positively.

Table 4. Sentiment Analysis on the effect on different disability types of Negative and Positive effect

Type of Disabilities	Very Negative effect	Negative effect	Somewhat Negative effect	Neutral	Somewhat positive effect	Positive effect	Very positive effect
Physical disability	0%	2.33%	2.33%	23.26%	15.12	43.02%	13.95%
Visual impairment	0%	2.33%	6.98%	25.58	25.58%	31.40%	8.14%
Hearing impairment	0%	3.49%	9.30%	23.26%	23.26%	31.40%	9.30%
Intellectual disability	0%	4.65%	12.79%	25.58%	22.90%	29.07%	5.81%

To understand whether one type of disability is better accepted by participants, data were gathered to determine whether one type of disability has a more negative or positive effect on an individual. The analysis of the pentagonal chart with the blue shape indicates that the majority of participants do not perceive a disability to positively influence their evaluation of customer satisfaction, suggesting a neutral impact on service quality. This observation is consistent across all four disability types, indicating that the perceived effect on customer satisfaction and service quality is not substantial. Conversely, the pentagonal chart with the red shaded area suggests a negative perception of service quality and customer satisfaction associated with disabilities. Despite, Figure 18 reveals that participants generally believe disabilities do not affect service quality and customer satisfaction, there is a noted fluctuation for perceived positive or negative effect connected to intellectual/mental disability. For intellectual/mental disability, customers revealed that it have a higher negative effect that positive effect.

Fig. 18. Perceived Positive / Negative impact on Service quality & Customer Satisfaction

The line graphs in Figure 19 represent survey responses where participants rated their satisfaction with service quality and overall customer satisfaction on a scale from 1 to 7, with 1 being poor and 7 being good. The red line across the graphs represents a neutral service level, rated at 3.5 out of 7. The graphs compare the perceived service quality and customer satisfaction when served by disabled persons (DP) versus non-disabled persons (NDP). Based on the survey results it seems that the service quality and customer satisfaction for services offered by disabled persons (DP) are perceived similarly to those offered by non-disabled persons (NDP). The data does not indicate a clear perception of better service quality or higher customer satisfaction for either group. Both DP and NDP fluctuate around the midpoint of 3.5 on the scale, suggesting that customers' experiences with service quality and satisfaction vary and do not consistently favor one group over the other. When asked to imagine the service quality and customer satisfaction offered by disabled persons (DP) and non-disabled persons (NDP), the concept of variability, the results indicate that the presence of a disabled person does not significantly alter the perceived service quality or customer satisfaction, as the variability in ratings is similar for both DP and NDP. This suggests that clients' perceptions are influenced more by the service experience itself rather than the provider's disability status.

Fig. 19. Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction variation for (Employee with disabilities Versus Non-disabled Employees)

To determine whether participants evaluate quality and satisfaction higher for employees with disabilities or without disabilities, a histogram was also constructed and shown in Figure 20. Referring to service quality for employees without disabilities, the histogram shows a wide distribution of scores, indicating variability. Whereas for

employees with Disabilities: The distribution is also wide, suggesting similar variability. Coming to Customer satisfaction, the score of employees without disabilities are more concentrated, indicating consistent customer satisfaction. Whereas for employee with disabilities, the distribution is spread out, showing variability in customer satisfaction. Therefore from the histograms, it appears that there is no clear indication that customers evaluate quality and satisfaction significantly higher for one group over the other. Both groups show variability in their scores.

Fig. 20. Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction variation for (Employee with disabilities Versus Non-disabled Employees)

The chart in Figure 21 represents a visual representation of how employees with disabilities are perceived in terms of two dimensions: As discussed in different research, a person with disabilities was usually perceived according to two dimension: Warmth and Competence. Our research shows that the dimension that reflects the friendliness and approachability (Warmth dimension), indicates a significant positive perception, with a majority 60% rating them highly. For the Competence Dimension, it measures the perceived ability and skill level of employees with disabilities. Again, the majority 50% perceive high competence, suggesting that employees with disabilities are largely seen as capable in effecting their roles.

Fig. 21. Stereotyping Analysis

The thematic analysis of emotional responses towards disabled employees in the workplace reveals different types of reactions that vary by gender. As shown in Table 4, Women’s responses range from negative emotions, such as fear and sadness about the safety and livelihood of disabled individuals, to neutral reactions of surprise and acknowledgment of unusual experiences. The majority of female participants, expressed admiration, awareness, and empathy, highlighting the determination and potential of disabled employees. On the other hand, Male participants, exhibit negative sentiments like cultural disconnection and sadness when served by disabled individuals. Their neutral feeling is marked by confusion over changing emotional reactions. Although Female participants have more positive sentiments, both Female and Male participants share common feelings such as admiration and empathy, with an added layer of diversity appreciation and personal connections to disability.

Table 5. Stereotyping Thematic Analysis

Gender:	Emotion Variance	Phrase
Female	Negative	Exposing to disability creates a sentiment of fear.
		It's sad to see a disabled person working for a living.
		Preoccupied that an issue could happen during the service phase.
	Neutral	Surprise by this unusual experience
		Behavior acknowledgment.
	Positive	Admiration for determination.
		Awareness of disability.
		Emotional reaction.
		Empathy towards disabled employees.
		Happy that professional opportunity is offered to employees with disability.
Pride in inclusivity.		
Recognizing potential.		

		Respect the effort made by employees with disabilities.
		Sadness acknowledgment.
		They have the same skills as non-disabled persons.
Male	Negative	Not part of our Culture
		It's triggers Sadness
		You always expect to be served by people who are fully fit.
	Neutral	Don't know the reason for this change of emotional reaction
	Positive	Admiration for determination.
		Diversity appreciation
		It is a natural feeling to perceive a positive feeling
		Empathy towards disabled employees.
		Need to be more patient during the interaction
My personal experience with relative having a disability		
Pride to observe inclusivity in workplace environment		
		Shocked with this unusual experience

7 Data Interpretation

The interpretation of data gathered is the core purpose of this paper, the interpretation and analysis are constructed on four hypotheses that explore various dimensions of service quality, emotional reactions, and customer familiarity with disability, and their effects on customer satisfaction. This Chapter explain and interpret these four hypothesis with the objective of contributing to the literature.

H1: Service quality has a significant direct effect on customer satisfaction in a disability inclusion context.

According to the SERVQUAL model, service quality is a construct that includes tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. This hypothesis suggests that service quality will significantly and directly affect customer satisfaction even in a disability inclusion context.

To understand whether service quality affects customer Satisfaction in the context of disability inclusion, correlation test was effected and the results provided in table 5 reveal a strong positive relationship between service quality for employees with disabilities and customer satisfaction. This significant correlation support our hypothesis that even when served by employees with disabilities, service quality will affect Customer Satisfaction [21]. The Pearson Correlation coefficient is 0.798, indicating a robust positive correlation. This suggests that as the perceived service quality increases, customer satisfaction also rises significantly, even when the service is provided by employees with disabilities. The significance level (Sig. 2-tailed) is 0.000, which is well below the 0.01 threshold, confirming that this correlation is statistically significant and not due to random chance. With a sample size (N) of 86, the data is substantial enough to support these findings.

Table 6. Correlation Test Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction in the context of Disability Inclusion

Correlations			
		Avg. SERVICE QUALITY_ EMPLOYEE DISABILITIES	Avg. CUSTOMER SATISFACTIO N_ EMPLOYEE DISABILITIES
Avg. SERVICE QUALITY_ EMPLOYEE DISABILITIES	Pearson Correlation	1	.798**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	86	86
Avg. CUSTOMER SATISFACTIO N_ EMPLOYEE DISABILITIES	Pearson Correlation	.798**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	86	86

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

These results imply that the SERVQUAL model, which assesses service quality is applicable in circumstances involving employees with disabilities. The strong correlation demonstrates that high service quality, regardless of the employees’ disabilities, leads to higher customer satisfaction. This implies that regardless of having an employee with disability or an employee without disability, customer will assess service based on five dimensions: tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy. This contribute to managerial knowledge by highlighting the importance of maintaining high service standards and ensuring that employees with disabilities are well-trained and supported to deliver quality service. By doing so, organizations can enhance customer satisfaction and demonstrate inclusivity and commitment to diversity. This analysis reinforces the relevance of the SERVQUAL model in diverse service environments, including those involving disabled employees. Therefore employees with disabilities can be valuable assets to an institution and deserve societal inclusion, which can be facilitated by ensuring their financial independence through job allocations.

H2: Higher levels of positive emotional reactions towards a disabled employee lead to increase service quality evaluation and thus customer satisfaction

H3: Higher levels of Negative emotional reactions towards a disabled employee lead to decrease service quality evaluation and thus customer satisfaction

This hypothesis advances that higher levels of positive emotional reactions towards an employee with disability can lead to increased customer satisfaction, with the perceived emotional reaction of participants serving as a mediator. Wegge et al. [40] provide evidence of a relationship between positive affect and satisfaction, suggesting that customers who feel positively about a service provider’s inclusivity may report higher satisfaction. For the purpose of this paper, participants were requested to state their emotional state at the end of the questionnaire. This enables the identification of any changes in emotional state after imagining different scenarios involving a person with a disability. These emotional states are then categorized according to their valence, either as positive valence or negative valence. Emotional valence refers to the intrinsic

attractiveness (positive valence) or averseness (negative valence) of an emotion, object, event, or situation.

Table 6 illustrated below analyzes the relationship between the perceived service quality of participants when served by an employees with disabilities and their emotional states. It shows a negative correlation of -0.290, indicating that as the perceived service quality decreases, negative emotions increase. This correlation is statistically significant, with a significance level of 0.007, meaning the result is reliable and not due to random chance. The analysis is based on 86 observations, providing a meaningful insight into how service quality impacts the emotional well-being of employees. This implies that when perceived service quality is closely related to the emotion state of an individual with disabilities.

Table 7. Correlation Test Emotional Valence (Positive or Negative) and Service Quality in the context of Disability Inclusion

Correlations			
		Avg. SERVICE_ QUALITY_ EMPLOYEE_ DISABILITIES	POSITIVE_ OR_ NEGATIVE_ EMOTION
Avg. SERVICE_QUALITY_ EMPLOYEE_ DISABILITIES	Pearson Correlation	1	-.290**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.007
	N	86	86
POSITIVE_OR_ NEGATIVE_EMOTION	Pearson Correlation	-.290**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.007	
	N	86	86
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Further testing was made to analyze the impact of perceived positive and negative emotional reaction on customer satisfaction evaluation and service quality. The box plot graph in Figure 22, shows that customer satisfaction varies based on these emotional valence. As per observation, participants tend to be more satisfied when they perceive emotions as positive, as indicated by higher median satisfaction scores in the 'Positive' category. Inversely, negative emotions correlate with lower customer satisfaction, as seen in the 'Negative' category. The 'Neutral' category falls somewhere in between. The spread of the box plots also indicates the consistency of responses; a narrower box suggests more consistent satisfaction ratings, while a wider box indicates greater variability in customer experiences. This implies that emotional valence is crucial in enhancing customer satisfaction, triggering positive emotions will improve customer satisfaction while negative valence will decrease it, since the presence of employees with disabilities is more often related to positive valence this implies that positive valence and thus higher customer satisfaction will more often occur for companies employing employee with disabilities. The box-and-whisker plot for service quality shows how participants' perceived emotions (positive, negative, or neutral) relate to the quality of service they perceived. The plot indicates that service quality varies with different emotional valence. For example, participants with positive emotions tend to

perceive higher service quality, while those with negative emotions show lower service quality. The plot helps to visualize that emotions significantly impact the level of service quality perceived by participants when served by employees with disabilities.

Fig. 22. Box plot Customer Satisfaction/Service quality and perceived emotional valence

H4: Customer familiarity to disability dimension has a significant direct effect on service quality and customer satisfaction in a disability inclusion context

The final hypothesis assumed that customer familiarity to disability dimension has a significant effect on the evaluation [42], of customer satisfaction in a disability inclusion context. The mediator in this case would be the personal disposition of the individual towards disability. Therefore individuals who are more familiar with disabilities may be more satisfied with the service, as they may have a more empathetic view of the service interaction.

The box plot in Figure 23, compares the service quality evaluations between participants who have a close relative with a disability and those who do not. The data shows that for those who stated that they have a close relative who have a disability, the median service quality score is around 5.5 and it is the same for those who answered no. There are outliers at approximately 3.0 and 6.8. The median service quality scores are similar for both groups, suggesting that having a relative with a disability does not significantly affect the evaluation of service quality. The Interquartile range (IQR) and whiskers show comparable variability in scores for both groups. The presence of outliers in the “Yes” category indicates some variability, but overall, the evaluations are consistent. This analysis suggests that participants’ evaluations of service quality are not significantly influenced by whether they have a relative with a disability. The same analysis was made for customer satisfaction. The median customer satisfaction scores are similar for both groups, suggesting that having a relative with a disability does not significantly affect the evaluation of customer satisfaction. The IQRs and whiskers show comparable variability in scores for both groups. The presence of outliers in the “Yes” category indicates some variability, but overall, the evaluations are consistent. This analysis suggests that participants’ evaluations of customer satisfaction are not significantly influenced by whether they have a relative with a disability.

Fig. 23. Box plot Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction V/S Familiarity to Disability

This finding is in contrary with the finds of Weinfield et al [42], who stated that an individuals with secure attachment histories, which can be influenced by having a close relative with a disability, are more responsive to and caring for others. Therefore it implies that such individual will demonstrate more empathic and positive reactions toward employees with a disability. Therefore to validate this finding, another statistical test was performed. The new chart in figure 23, displays the service quality scores for employees with disabilities based on whether respondents have a close relative or family member who has a disability. The chart includes error bars representing the 83% confidence interval for each group. The X-axis represent participant response to whether they have a close relative who have a disability "Yes" and "No" , while the Y-axis represents the mean service quality scores. The mean for service quality scores for both groups ("Yes" and "No") are very close, around 5.5. The error bars, representing the 83% confidence intervals, overlap significantly. This suggests that there is no statistically significant difference between the two groups' mean service quality scores. The chart indicates that having a close relative or family member with a disability does not significantly affect the average service quality score given by respondents. The overlapping error bars suggest that any observed difference in mean scores is likely due to random variation rather than a true underlying difference.

Analysis was also made to evaluate the effect of Gender on Customer satisfaction evaluation, as shown in Figure 25. As per hereunder we could observe that Female participants evaluation customer satisfaction with higher scoring on a scale of 1 to 7, where 1 is poor service and 7 is excellent service. This trend implies that females might have a more positive perception of the services provided by employees with disabilities compared to male participants.

Fig. 24. Box plot (Mean Analysis) Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction V/S Familiarity to Disability

Fig. 25. Histogram Customer Satisfaction versus Gender

H 5: Gender has a significant direct effect on stereotyping in the context of disability inclusion. The mediator would be analyzing and measuring the warmth and competence evaluation.

The box plot graph in Figure 26 shows the perceived warmth (friendliness) of employees with disabilities based on the gender of the respondents. The x-axis categorizes respondents into “Female,” “Male,” and other gender categories, while the y-axis measures the warmth on a scale from 1.00 to 7.00. From the graph in Figure 26, it appears that female respondents generally perceive disabled employees as more friendly compared to male respondents. This is indicated by a higher median value in the “Female” category. The interquartile range (IQR) for females is also higher, suggesting that a larger proportion of female respondents rated disabled employees more favorably. In contrast, male respondents have a lower median and a narrower IQR, indicating less variability and generally lower warmth ratings.

This analysis was also repeated for the competence dimension. From the graph in Figure 26, it appears that female respondents generally perceive disabled employees as more competent compared to male respondents. This is indicated by a higher median value in the “Female” category. The interquartile range (IQR) for females is also higher, suggesting that a larger proportion of female respondents rated disabled employees more favorably. In contrast, male respondents have a lower median and a narrower IQR, indicating less variability and generally lower competence ratings. The presence of outliers, especially in the ‘Male’ category, shows that some male respondents rated competence significantly differently from the majority.

This analysis highlights a gender difference in perceptions in a context of disability inclusion on the workplace environment, with females tending to view disabled employees more positively in terms of competence and warmth compared to male.

Fig. 26. Stereotyping Analysis from a Gender perspective

To validate this hypothesis, a histogram comparison to compare responses from the different gender category. The bar graphs compare different genders’ perceptions and it could be concluded that for warmth dimension, “Female” generally perceived higher warmth and competence from employee with disabilities compared to males. Overall, females tend to perceive higher warmth and competence in disabled employees compared to other genders in a workplace environment.

Fig. 27. Histogram Stereotyping Analysis

8 Final Conclusion

This study revealed that the majority of participants tend to remain neutral regarding whether their service providers have disabilities. This neutrality suggests that most people prioritize the quality of service over the personal attributes of the service providers. This finding reinforces existing literature, which demonstrates that service quality is closely linked to customer satisfaction. However, the study also highlighted a subtle yet significant difference in attitudes based on gender. Females, in particular, demonstrated a slightly higher level of empathy towards service providers with disabilities. This increased empathy among women may originate from broader social and cultural factors that encourage supportive behaviors. Additionally, it was shown that when disability inclusion is perceived positively, it influences the evaluation of service quality and thus

customer satisfaction. Overall, the findings suggest a generally inclusive attitude, with a notable trend towards empathy among female respondents.

Societal contribution.

This paper provides insightful contributions to both societal and managerial aspects by focusing on the importance of service quality and customer satisfaction in the context of disability inclusion. The document demonstrate that the SERVQUAL model also applies to the context of disability inclusion. One of the main findings of this research is that the emotional state of individuals affect the perception of service quality and thus customer satisfaction. As shown in this paper, positive emotional reactions towards employees with disabilities significantly enhance customer satisfaction. This is crucial for the societal integration of individual with disabilities. By promoting a more inclusive environment where individuals with disabilities are valued and respected, this paper forges the foundation for additional research that will help in promoting societal inclusion of individuals with a disability in a workplace environment. Additionally by advocating the financial independence of individuals with disabilities through job allocations, it is not only empowering this segment of our society but also demonstrating a commitment to diversity and inclusivity in the workforce. This paper is in connection with the recent parliamentary debates in Mauritius, which highlights that achieving such inclusion is a huge challenge. As stated during the parliamentary debate of Tuesday 16 April 2024:

“Several countries have faced challenges in implementing comprehensive disability laws, often due to various factors such as political dynamics, budget constraints and societal attitudes. In India, for example, the Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act was passed in 2016, replacing the Persons with Disabilities Act of 1995. Despite all its efforts, it took India over two decades – 20 years, Mr Speaker, Sir – to enact a revised and more inclusive law...” [16].

This demonstrates the colossal effort that awaits Governmental and institutional bodies to achieve such inclusion in today’s world. The main challenge is to make disability inclusion seem normal, while it is usually regarded as an abnormal phenomenon. Hopefully, the human nature and its cognitive abilities permits to have faith in achieving such inclusion. As demonstrated in this paper, genetic characters usually featured us to react in a certain manner. Taking the example of Female respondents who generally perceive disabled employees more positively in terms of warmth and competence compared to male respondents. This highlights an encouraging pattern for a societal shift towards more inclusive and empathetic perspectives in workplace environments. This paper demonstrate that by employing individuals with disabilities and ensuring that training is provided to maintain high service quality, businesses can foster societal acceptance and appreciation for diversity. As demonstrated, employing individuals with disabilities can lead to lower rates of staff turnover and absenteeism for businesses. Additionally, it has been shown that customers are more likely to recommend and promote businesses that employ individuals with disabilities through positive word of mouth. A significant contribution of this paper is the finding that the involvement of individuals with disabilities often triggers positive emotions, which in turn positively influence customer satisfaction and service quality evaluations. All these factors

contribute positively to the institution's image. Furthermore, for society and governmental bodies, individuals with disabilities represent an additional workforce that can aid in economic growth and social welfare. This inclusive approach also enhances the image of governmental bodies and improves public opinion. To conclude, as stated during parliamentary debates the ultimate objective of this paper is to ensure that:

“All our children enjoy the same rights and that no one is left behind. UNESCO puts it beautifully: we want all our children to enjoy the same rights” [16].

Managerial Contribution.

Apart from a societal contribution, this paper also provides insight to managerial perspective. The document provides several key insights that can enhance business operations and customer satisfaction. As demonstrated during the Meta-Analysis, across various industries, high service quality is a crucial determinant of customer satisfaction and loyalty. The Meta-Analysis also demonstrate the applicability of the SERVQUAL model to adapt in contexts involving employees with disabilities, emphasizing the need of ensuring that service standard are maintained. To maintain the service standard, ensuring that employees with disabilities are well-trained and supported is essential. By employing individuals with disabilities, businesses would enhances customer satisfaction but also demonstrate that the company is committed to diversity and inclusion. This demonstration would be beneficial for both individuals with disability and organizations, since it was demonstrated during this research that promoting “diversity and inclusion” is the reason why individuals highly evaluate the service quality, advocate positive word of mouth and high Net Promoter Scores (NPS).

Based on the conclusions drawn, the recommendation of this paper would be to promote Inclusivity and Diversity. As demonstrated during the research, organizations should actively promote inclusivity by employing individuals with disabilities and providing them with the necessary training and support to be able to provide high quality service. This not only improves customer satisfaction that resulted in higher financial gain and increasing brand image, but also contributes to societal acceptance of diversity. However, business should focus on maintaining high service quality across all dimensions of the SERVQUAL model. Additionally, the meta-analysis shows that it is important to implement sector-specific strategies to enhance service quality. Taking the example of the hotel industry it was shown that such business should prioritize food quality and cleanliness [48]. Professionals in the hospitality industry, particularly within hotels, would benefit from understanding that the quality of food in specialized restaurants, room cleanliness, and buffet food quality are paramount in enhancing guest satisfaction., While in the aviation industry, customer comfort, facilitated by high-quality facilities such as comfortable cabins, seats, and clean toilets, significantly impacts satisfaction [49]. Similarly, in the telecommunications sector, dimensions like tangibility, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy are critical for achieving high service quality and enhancing customer satisfaction [46]. Finally, in the banking sector it has been demonstrated that customer loyalty is strongly influenced by satisfaction and awareness, with service quality playing a pivotal role in retaining customers. To distinguish themselves from competitors, banks should prioritize investments in advanced

technology and high-quality products and services [47]. This demonstrate that adapting to the industry is crucial when applying the SERVQUAL model.

Yet, these are some universal findings that are applicable to all industries. It was shown that investing in customer experience mediators, such as knowledgeable staff, empathetic interactions, and a pleasant environment, is crucial for achieving high customer satisfaction. More importantly, maximizing on positive affect event that arouse positive valence could serve as a positive advantage for businesses. As it was demonstrated that the inclusion of employee with disability within the workplace environment is considered as being an event that triggers positive emotions, it would be beneficial for both (employee and the employer) to be advocate of disability inclusion.

This paper advocates for the promotion of disability inclusion and not exploitation of those individuals for competitive advantage. The difference is that a societal inclusion will facilitate the financial independence of individuals with disabilities by providing job opportunities and ensuring fair compensation. This approach not only empowers individuals but also fosters a positive organizational image. By implementing these recommendations, governmental bodies and businesses could significantly enhance economic indicators, social welfare and provide managerial insight, which will lead to higher customer satisfaction, loyalty, and overall business success and more importantly ensure that “our children enjoy the same rights” [16].

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